

NANOCELLULOSE AS OXYGEN BARRIER MATERIAL: FROM FILM FORMING PROPERTIES TO THERMALLY ACTIVATED COATINGS FOR PACKAGING

Pieter Samyn

SIRRIS – Smart Coatings Lab, Diepenbeek, Belgium

Original scientific paper
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5256183
pieter.samyn@sirris.be

Abstract: *In answer to the ban for traditional plastics and need for more sustainable packaging solutions, paper-based materials became into focus. However, their performance towards oxygen permeability and water sensitivity needs to be improved with a coating layer that does not interfere with recyclability of the paper. The production of nanocelluloses provides unique types of cellulose materials with high crystallinity and formation of a dense fiber network structure with low oxygen permeability. Moreover, a feasibility study has proven that they can be obtained by processing of residual sludge fractions and processing water from the traditional papermaking process. After years of academic research, industrial readiness of nanocellulose production has been established. For both types of cellulose nanocrystals or cellulose nanofibrils, the mechanisms for creating barrier layers either as a free-standing film or paper coating are reviewed. In particular, the morphology of the cellulose fibrils strongly relates to the formation of a dense films with sufficient barrier properties. As a main hurdle, however, the water sensitivity fully degrades the protective material under humid conditions due to swelling and reduction in strength of the hydrogen bonding network. While the stability of nanocellulose can be increased through traditional chemical surface modification and/or addition of plasticizer, a novel concept is presented that includes the thermally activated release of encapsulated waxes from hydrophobic nanoparticles deposited onto the fibrillar surfaces. As such, a novel generation of nanocellulose nanocomposite materials with improved barrier properties over a broad range of humidity is created.*

Keywords: paper, coating, nanocellulose, barrier properties

1 INTRODUCTION

The various forms of nanocellulose such as CNC (crystalline nanocellulose) and MFC/NFC (micro- or nanofibrillated cellulose) exist with different morphologies depending on the fiber size and abilities for formation of a dense fiber network. The high polarities of their structures beneficially contribute to increased interactions between the fibrils, which are interconnected to each other through hydrogen bonds and van der Waals attractive forces. The nanocelluloses consequently have inherent properties to form high barrier properties against oxygen, but the performance is strongly dependent on different fiber characteristics and processing conditions of the nanocellulose. The differences in oxygen permeability for CNC and CNF can be described through its morphology (Wang et al., 2018). As the CNF has high aspect ratio and entangles into a dense structure, a network with small pore sizes and high tortuosity for diffusion of molecules is created. The CNC presents more rigid fibers that easily arrange into a layered structure with lower volume fraction of voids and higher density. A more definitive understanding should be ascertained regarding the oxygen barrier property when comparing CNFs and CNCs (Wang et al., 2020).

The penetration of oxygen through the fibrillar network depends on solubility and diffusion. The polarity of the cellulose is different than the oxygen, therefore reducing the solubility and restricting the adsorption of oxygen. The formation of a dense packaging with small pore sizes reduces the permeability of the gas molecules (Lavoine et al., 2012). The presence of a high density of hydrogen bonds in the cellulosic fiber network induces high cohesive energy with large activation potential for the migration of the molecules.

Different parameters of the cellulose nanofibers influence the oxygen transmission rate (OTR). The source of production and pretreatment of MFC influence OTR, e.g. by TEMPO-oxidation (Vartianen et al., 2015). A lower OTR was observed with increasing amount of oxidation and the transmission values for the MFC produced from Spruce were inferior to those for Eucalyptus pulp (Rodionova et al. 2012). In particular, the microstructure of MFC related to the OTR (Chinga-Carrasco et al. 2012), as the relatively thick and poorly fibrillated fibers result in films with relatively high porosity. Otherwise, the density of the films increased after TEMPO-oxidation and a linear decrease in OTR with degree of modification was observed (Rodionova et al., 2011).

The deposition of MFC/NFC as a paper coating can be done following traditional coating methods, including spin-, dip- spray- or rod-coating. As a result, the MFC forms a dense and oriented surface layer. The interactions between the cellulose paper substrate and the coating are critical, as voids can occur due to insufficiently smooth shear and high interactions between the coating and base substrate. Therefore, the direct application under wet conditions is considered (Syverud et al. 2009). In particular, the thick coatings are needed in order to obtain full coverage of the surface without tendency for microcracking. Alternatively, plasticizers such as sorbitol or glycerol can be added to form more thick and defect-free MFC coatings.

Above all, the high water-sensitivity of MFC/NFC coatings strongly deteriorates OTR performances. Therefore, the surface modification through acetylation of the MFC in presence of acetic anhydride was performed to introduce hydrophobic properties, while providing low OTR over a broad range of humidity conditions (Rodionova et al. 2012). The addition of sorbitol or glycerol plasticizers similarly provided better protection of the fibrillar coatings against environmental humidity changes, in parallel with the densification of the coating structure through hot-pressing (Van Ngyen et al., 2021).

In view of the intrinsic properties of MFC/NFC creating an oxygen barrier layer, novel concepts for activated packaging coatings can be developed taking into account additional hydrophobic protection. Therefore, proof-of-concept for a new mechanism controlling hydrophobicity and OTR of MFC/NFC networks is presented, through the surface modification of the MFC fibrils by deposition of hydrophobic nanoparticles with encapsulated wax. The controlled wax release upon functionalization additionally contributes to the formation of a full protection film. In parallel with considerations for higher efficiency in the circular use of natural resources, alternative ways for the production of MFC/NFC from sludge residues of pulp- and papermills are considered in contrast with traditional cellulose resources.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

A sample was collected of primary sludge from a paper mill (Brazil), which was pretreated through dilution, intensive washing and filtration of the sludge suspension. A mild acidic pretreatment was performed for neutralization of the CaCO_3 , in presence of sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid and acetic acid. The acid agent was diluted in aqueous conditions and added in a suspension of 250 ml containing 5 g (dry weight) of sludge. The ratio of chemical agents was calculated from the stoichiometric reaction ratio with CaCO_3 . The suspension remained agitated for few minutes and was cleaned over a screen of 60 mesh

and 10 cm diameter. The retained materials were intensively washed with distilled water until neutral pH and filtered again. After pretreatment, the ash and CaCO₃ contents in the recovered sample were checked by analytical methods and reduced to zero.

The production of MFC/NFC from recovered sample was done in a microfluidizer (type EH-110, Microfluidics, Westwood, MA), using a diluted suspension of 2 wt.-% solid content. The sample was processed through 25 steps in a homogenizer chamber and 10 steps in a 200 µm chamber. Subsequently, the surface modification was done through deposition of hydrophobic nanoparticles, including poly(styrene-co-maleimide) and wax, as detailed before (Rastogi et al., 2016).

3 TEST RESULTS

3.1 Film forming properties

The coatings of the modified MFC were applied onto a sheet of base paper. Where the initial unmodified MFC formed an open film structure, the surface-modified MFC allowed to form a film with a more dense fiber packing and low porosity. The interface between the coating and the paper substrate was difficult for the pure MFC due to instabilities in the shear properties and uneven deposition during bar-coating process. In contrast, the coatings with modified MFC were more homogeneous and the interface with the paper substrate was better developed, partly due to the better shear and lubricating properties of the encapsulated wax particles. A detail of the modified fibers with wax particle deposits can be observed through AFM analysis, showing good interactions between the particles and cellulose fibers. The fiber surfaces are homogeneously covered, while maintaining the morphology of a thin fibrillar network structure. In a further upscaling experiment, the spray coating application of the dispersions was optimized in order to build coatings with grammage 8 g/m² providing the full surface coverage. The morphology of the different coatings is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Scanning electron microscopy of oxygen barrier coatings, including (a) native MFC, (b) surface-modified MFC (AFM inset scanning size $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$)

3. 2 Thermally activated coatings for packaging

The activated coatings were created through thermal heating of the modified MFC, resulting in the progressive release of wax from the encapsulated polymer matrix. Consequently, the morphology of the coating evolved and formed a more continuous layer upon exposure of the wax. The latter has a function of plasticizer that consequently benefits the formation of a closed surface layer. Due to the presence of the MFC network, the diffusion of the wax into the porous bulk of the paper substrate was limited and the coating rather forms a closed top layer, as shown in Figure 2.

In parallel, the OTR values for the different samples were measured at relative humidity of 50 % and 70 %, under controlled temperature of 35 °C. The test results of OTR are expressed in Table 1, where values for uncoated paper could not be measured (out-of-range), while significant improvement in the OTR values for MFC coatings was observed at humidity of 50 %. However, the increase in humidity has a detrimental effect on OTR values for unmodified MFC coatings. The OTR values for modified MFC coatings are lower than unmodified MFC coatings (both 8 g/m^2), while they also remain more constant at high humidity. The coatings with modified MFC were subsequently thermally heated for the release of wax at temperatures $T = 135 \text{ °C}$ and $T = 180 \text{ °C}$, resulting in a further decrease of OTR owing to the release of wax and formation of a defect-free film on the paper substrate.

Figure 2: Paper coatings with modified MFC after thermal heating at different temperatures, resulting in thermally activated release of wax.

Table 1: OTR values [$\text{cm}^3/(\text{m}^2 \text{ day})$] for different coatings on paper (8 g/m^2)

	RH = 50 %	RH = 70 %
Unmodified MFC coating	$3.8 \cdot 10^3$	$8.5 \cdot 10^3$
Modified MFC coating $T = 23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$2.1 \cdot 10^3$	$2.8 \cdot 10^3$
$T = 135 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$1.4 \cdot 10^3$	$1.8 \cdot 10^3$
$T = 180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^3$	$1.2 \cdot 10^3$

4 CONCLUSIONS

The coatings with MFC can be smoothly applied onto packaging paper grades with a reduction in oxygen barrier transmission. Alternatively, the hydrophobic surface modification of the MFC provides better protection with less dependence on the environmental humidity through thermally activated release of wax. Therefore, the presented system may be a good candidate for combined hydrophobic and oxygen barrier properties with good film forming properties when applied as paper coating.

5 REFERENCES

Chinga-Carrasco G., Syverud K. (2012). On the structure and oxygen transmission rate of biodegradable cellulose nanobarriers, *Nanoscale Res Lett* 7, p. 192.

Lavoine N., Desloges I., Dufresne A., Bras J. (2012). Microfibrillated cellulose – its barrier properties and applications in cellulosic materials, a review. *Carbohydr Polym* 90, pp. 735-764.

Rastogi V.K., Stanssens D., Samyn P. (2016). Reaction efficiency and retention of poly(styrene-co-maleimide) nanoparticles deposited on fibrillated cellulose surfaces. *Carbohydr Polym* 141, pp. 244-252.

Rodionova G., Lenes M., Eriksen O., Gregson O. (2011). Surface chemical modification of microfibrillated cellulose : improvement of barrier properties for packaging applications. *Cellulose* 18, pp. 127-134.

Rodionova G., Saito T., Lenes M., Erikson O., Gregersen O., Fukuzumi H., Isogai A. (2012). Mechanical and oxygen barrier properties of films prepared from fibrillated dispersions of TEMPO-oxydized Norway spruce and eucalyptus pulps. *Cellulose* 19, pp. 705-711.

Syverud K., Stenius P. (2009). Strength and barrier properties of MFC films. *Cellulose* 16, pp. 75-85.

Vartiainen J., Lahtinen P., Kaljunen T., Kunnari V., Peresin M.S., Tammelin T. (2015). Comparison of properties between cellulose nanofibrils made from banana, sugar beet, hemp, softwood and hardwood pulps. *Revista o Papel* 76, pp. 51-54.

Van Nguyen S., Lee B.K. (2021). Microfibrillated cellulose films with enhanced mechanical and water-resistant properties by glycerol and hot-pressing treatment. *Cellulose*, in press.

Wang J., Gardner D.J., Stark N.M., Bousfield D.W., Tajvidi M., Cai Z. (2018). Moisture and oxygen barrier properties of cellulose nanomaterial-based films. *ACS Sus Chem Eng* 6, pp. 49-70.

Wang L., Chen C., Wang J., Gardner D.J., Tajvidi M. (2020). Cellulose nanofibrils versus cellulose nanocrystals: comparison of performance in flexible multilayer films for packaging applications. *Food Pack Shelf Life* 23, 100464.